

THE ROLE OF MORAL EDUCATION IN THE FAMILY IN DEFENSE AGAINST IDEOLOGICAL THREATS

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"The future of our planet, its well-being, how are our children It is related to human development. Our main task is necessary for young people to show their potential. Creating conditions, spreading the "virus" of the idea of violence prevention"

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev
From his speech at the 72nd session of the UN

Annotation: The article examines the importance of upbringing highly moral youth and intergenerational conflicts in the family. Today's rapidly evolving globalization is taking on a new meaning in the spirituality of every nation, people, nation, or humanity. In the development of society, "just as every social phenomenon has its pros and cons, so does the process of globalization. But along with such achievements, we must not forget that globalization poses a spiritual threat to the national ideas, ideologies, beliefs and heritage of some peoples. The author examines the role of the family in the upbringing of a comprehensively mature and harmoniously developed generation and notes its responsibility for resolving issues of intergenerational interactions.

Keywords: countries of the world, interaction, globalization, social phenomenon, integration, foreign investment, capital and goods, modern communications, information technology, science, environmental disasters, The Process Of Globalization, National Ideology, Regional And Regional, International Education, National Pride, Alternative, National Pride, National Pride, Nation Of Nationalities, Public Policy. family, conflict, high spirituality, society, research, emotional alienation, conflict relationships, inner experiences

INTRODUCTION

The socio-political development and future of any multi-ethnic country where there is a variety of nations and future will be close to interethnic relations.

This issue requires an impaired approach is very relevant for the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is included in the sentence of multinational countries. The independence requires comprehensive and deep study of the content of national foundations of foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. As a result of independence of our country, radical changes have emerged in existing socio-political processes. From the first days of independence, Uzbekistan has given great attention to the development of international relations and has gained a unique experience in stabilizing interethnic relations in a multinational country.

This is followed by educating national pride and pride, to restore and restore the culture, language, traditions of nations, to preserve the culture of nations, to achieve general consent solar in the country. Therefore, the creation of a legal framework for the maintenance of interethnic harmony and the equality of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan has risen to the level of maintaining interethnic harmony in society in the structure of various uniformity of the Republic of Uzbekistan. A number of practical measures have been taken in this regard. It should be noted that improving inter-ethnic relations is a special responsibility to Uzbeks, which are a statenation, and historically lives in this space. The role of the family in raising the comprehensive mature and harmoniously developed generation is unique and unchanged. Family is the smallest cell of society, and the future development of society and people is inextricably linked by the family.

After all, the basics of education are laid in the family. According to A. Avloni: "Education must be started to strengthen their body, to enlighten the mind, decorate our morality, to educate the mind. There is a question who is engaged in education? In the first upbringing. This is the duty of the mother. High school and madrasa. This is the debt of the father, teacher and government ". Indeed, education is a complex process that provides an accurate and objective perception of man itself and their behavior. It is the pillars of the family - parents - are responsible for performing this complex process. This requires the right organization of family education from parents. Because the main criterion of any education is to form the right ideas about yourself and those surrounding it.

REFERENCES AND METHODS

The article discusses the importance of intergenerational conflicts in the family of today's Uzbek youth. The nature of the national ideology in the process of globalization is clearly demonstrating in the concept of the new Uzbek-newly worldvaist. The fact that the development of the development carried out under the leadership of the head of our state is that it is not only economic development, but

also a broader national revival and social development. He, first of all, he based the independent national development of the Republic of Uzbekistan necessitates the common theoretical opinions and targets that target the state aimed at achieving the established goals. In world linguistics, the assessment of the text and the existence of different approaches to this phenomenon are considered. In the process of scientific coverage of the article, objective, historical and logical methods of scientific knowledge were widely used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Another important question that parents should know and which must be followed, is to have a good idea of how to upbringing their children corresponds to the spirit of time, opportunities and needs of time. The national idea is inextricably linked with a new worldview of civil society and development in our country. The ideology has to identify itself for social groups, serve as a means of identifying its goals. The main conclusions and principles of development of a new worldview develop in Uzbekistan are expressed in the works of President Sh. Mirziyoyev. In particular, the essence, content, concepts and principles, unique features of the idea of "the new worldvaeva" is highlighted in the essence, content, concepts and principles of the "new worldvaeva". Studying these works not only to strengthen the socio-spiritual foundations of civil society in our country, but to resist the aggression of ideological gap in the context of globalization, are wellharmd people Deliver, through this, requires the necessity of national ideology in solving problems in strengthening interethnic harmony.

Under the context of globalization, the community of our society is taking place, in the form of thinking. The impact of the globalization process on the national idea, its conversion strength became the current world. This process increases their interaction, interaction, and does not reflect in national- spiritual and idle life in the life of different countries, peoples. Today not only in our spiritual and ideological life, but also changes in our lives are positive. The development of modern techniques and technology and the globalization of information dissemination, on the one hand, is becoming stronger tools, on the other hand, on the other hand, on the other hand. The national idea is becoming an integral part of the spiritual life of society, the program of individuals, social and ethnic groups. This is more needing to scientifically study the involvement of the national idea and the ethnic processes. The national idea of the National idea holds the role, peace and stability of the Republic of Uzbekistan, unites important aspects of the ideological immunity that can resist different and harmful ideas. The gear is increasingly important.

This means that in the eyes of parents, together with their cute children, they should have the future, inextricably related to the needs of society, the development of the nation. In turn, certain results can be achieved if the upbringing is based on traditions and customs formed for centuries. In short, if the biggest and invaluable legacy, which is left by the parents of the child, is good behavior and good deeds, it will be a worthy contribution to the care of the harmoniously developed generation. Since the first processes of the moral formation of young people, the creators of our future, our country, are given special attention to family education in our country. In the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is the highest document of the state, there is a separate chapter on the family, and Article 63 states that "the family is the main cell of society and has the right to defense from society." The achievement of harmony between the family - the community - the educational institution - the Society - the state is an important development condition ". Today, our state takes practical measures in this direction. In particular, on the development of children's sports so that they can do physical education from childhood. For example, various sports facilities were built for the development of children's sports and attract children to sports. As a result of such practical efforts, our children achieve high results in various sports fields. It goes without saying that the fate of the Motherland and its future requires special attention to the upbringing of our children today, their physical and spiritual health.

The achievement of physical maturity depends on the will of the person and is an important component of the social education system. Education is a process that affects the entire destiny of the child. In other words, if the child is a sapling, the parent is a gardener. However, there are periods when in any family there are complex relationships between family members. Family members do not understand or do not want to understand each other. As a result, there is a conflict between the "fathers" and "children", which is called inter-floor. The inter-generational conflict in the family was and remains very interesting and relevant to the study. Family malfunctions are caused by the impossibility of simultaneous satisfaction of the needs of older and younger generations, awareness of the participants in the conflict of infringement of their interests and attitude towards the opposing side of both the opponent and the "culprit" of the problem.

Even in ancient times at the tomb of the Egyptian pharaoh Amenophis 3rd, a fairly eloquent inscription was made: "Young stalls, without obedience and respect for the elder. The truth was discarded, customs do not recognize. No one understands them, and they themselves no longer want to be understood; Walk to the

world of death and become its last limit." Almost two thousand years ago, Socrates with bitterness stated: "The current youth is used to luxury. It is distinguished by bad manners, despises authorities, does not respect the elders. Children argue with parents. Even swallow food and make teachers." The teaching of Islam is destructive, panic, enmity and conspiracy in the hearts of people strongly condemns the scattering of seeds. It is known that in recent years, religion has become their own Disguised streams and categories appeared. They are on the way to their malicious goals increase in crimes such as vandalism in society, unjust bloodshed of innocent people they are trying to break the peace of citizens and create conflict among the people. In the process of globalization, people, especially young people, are seen in different ways special attention to a number of the following aspects in protecting against the influence of ideological attacks focus is necessary. In particular, he is always alert, alert and alert against ideological threats living sober. Promoting a healthy lifestyle among young people, formation of their spiritual and moral education, patriotism in the minds of young people, noble qualities such as humanity, kindness, honoring the honor of the country work is organized on the basis of family-neighborhood-educational institution cooperation reach. 64 Today's information is fast-paced and a prisoner of information attacks not turning So, in the 21st century, when the information struggle has intensified, young people are protected from ideological attacks increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational promotion work in protection, in-depth analysis of the positive changes happening in our lives conveying information to the younger generation, strengthening their social activity is more important than ever.

At all times, youth was in moral condemnation as a rapid passionate time and extremes. Almost all societies subdivide their members to age categories: youth, maturity and old age, although there are more fractional divisions. The purpose of youth-preparation to maturity, in the most complete assimilation of the dominant norms and values, whose keeper is old age. This chain of age periods in a person's life was inseparable and strictly linear. The critical perception of young people is largely caused by its inability to perceive the norms and values of the world of adults. And the great Socrates worked not as much as young people, how much for society as a whole, because, the failure of young people from the pastors of the past meant huge changes in the future device of society. That in the eyes of thinkers of that time was unacceptable and unacceptable. In the family, the inter-flow conflict is manifested in various forms: obviously or hidden: in the form of psychological pressure, emotional alienation, violent physical actions, material deprivation,

scandals, skirmishes, quarrels, contention,expulsion from family, rough and disregarding relationships, leaving helpless stateand etc. The family conflict varies on duration and sustainability. In some families, itis an episodic, short-term and even one-time. In others - long, relatively frequent,sustainable; It is based on more or less regular conflict relationships.

CONCLUSION

The behavior of participants in the family in the family depends on their sexuality. It affects the entry or avoidance of conflicts, conflict behavior strategy. Despite the fact that children consider their families happy in most of them conflicts happen. As penalties, unlike old times, bodily applied little, most conflicts remain on the verbal level. Despite the fact that historically the role of the head of the family has consolidated for a man, in modern society, a woman is more fulfilled, she brings up and, if possible, contains children. It should be said that young people have a healthy outlook on globalization

The time demands the development of a program aimed at development. To all of us it should be clear that wherever carelessness and indifference rule, there spirituality becomes the weakest and weakest point, and vice versa, where prudence and where enthusiasm reigns, spirituality becomes a powerful force. Especially Today, in the international arena, various political forces have their own national and strategic the true nature and goals of the far-sighted policy to achieve the plans educational, natural and social sciences it is important to notice and understand in time. In the process of globalization It is wiser than our national idea to protect young people from various spiritual threats for every member of society of our use, the reforms being implemented we must ensure that it is productive and useful. Youth in community development If we create a social environment free from moral threats, our tomorrow will be better Our young people will grow up to be children of a prosperous era. It happened between them The spiritual images that are taking place are always a new worldview and ideology it is envisaged that the processes will be directed towards the perspective of humanity and young people serves as an impetus for the development of topical issues in his spiritual life. As President Sh. Mirziyoyev noted, "The world is rapidly changing, various new ones that lead to stability and solid development of nations to spirituality and enlightenment today, when threats and dangers are emerging, moral education, paying attention to the desire of young people to learn and mature more important than ever."

Therefore, the mother burdened with such adouble social burden is discomfort, which is reflected in the fact that all the motherssurveyed by us noted that they

conflict with children more often than their spouses. However, the sample of the father is also important for the Son as in the former times. The fathers are easier to communicate with sons, young men, less spending time on a quarrel with them, in contrast to quarrels with mothers. But about the inner experiences still easier to share them with a mother than with his father, because any son in the eyes of the Father should be courageous, worthy, proud, strong. Making a family with the smallest link, which society can rely, we not only contribute to the development of the state, but also hinder the accession of our children to various alien and alien ideas. In this article we touched upon some aspects of inter-flow ties. In our opinion, work in this direction must be continued.

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